

AWARE2ALL: human centric interaction and safety systems for increasing the share of automated vehicles

Marcos Nieto¹[0000-0001-9879-0992], Oihana Otaegui¹[0000-0001-6069-8787], Maria Panou²[0000-0002-2161-9246], Christian Birkner³[0000-0002-2875-212X], Ondrej Vaculin³[0000-0002-8184-7240], and Ariadna Rodríguez⁴[0000-0003-0473-9366]

¹ Vicomtech, Donostia, Spain

² Hellenic Institute of Transport (CERTH), Thessaloniki, Greece

³ Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt, Ingolstadt, Germany

⁴ Capgemini, Barcelona, Spain

mnieto@vicomtech.org

Abstract. The AWARE2ALL project is designed to address the new challenges of Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) from a human-centric perspective. These vehicles will allow occupants to engage in non-driving activities, rising research questions about occupant behavior, activities, and Human-Machine Interfaces (HMI) to keep them aware of the situation and the automation mode. The project aims to ensure safe operation of HAVs by developing safety and HMI systems that provide a holistic understanding of the scene. This includes continuous monitoring of the interior situation and advanced passive safety systems for occupant safety, as well as a surround perception system and external HMI for the safety of Human Road Users (HRUs). AWARE2ALL is paving the way for HAV deployment by effectively addressing changes in road safety and interactions between different road users caused by the emergence of HAVs. It is developing innovative technologies, assessment tools, and methodologies to adapt to new scenarios in mixed traffic. The project builds on previous research and aims to mitigate new safety risks associated with the introduction of HAVs.

Keywords: Internal HMI, External HMI, Occupant Safety, HRU Safety.

1 Introduction

In 2020, one life was lost every 25 minutes in European roads, for a total of 18,844 fatalities. Shockingly, road accidents were the leading cause of death for individuals aged 5–14 and the second leading cause for those aged 15–29. Notably, over 46% of these fatalities in Europe in 2018 were comprised of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), including pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists. Troublingly, it was estimated that human error played a role in roughly 95% of all road traffic accidents.

Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) have the potential to improve road safety by reducing crashes due to driver error and also by representing an alternative to high-risk drivers (e.g., drunk or distracted drivers). However, HAVs may introduce additional safety risks that must be addressed: component failures, increased risk-taking,

unconventional seating position and occupant postures, increased vehicle travel, interaction with VRUs and also mixed traffic interacting with Human Driven Vehicles (HDVs)[1]. The obstacles for HAVs introduction in the market mainly come from safety and human factors concerns [2]. Hence, the expected new safety-critical situations must be addressed, especially those involving human road users (HRUs), that includes VRUs and HDVs.

2 AWARE2ALL Approach

2.1 Concept

The focus is to ensure reliable integral safety of the occupants with special attention to the new variety of possibilities that automated driving functions will bring to vehicle occupants (including leisure activities) and ensuring safe control transitions between SAE levels when necessary. The AWARE2ALL concept is supported by three main actions:

- development of an integral safety concept that automatically takes decisions according to the occupants’ state, overall situation (interior layout, exterior scene, etc.) to guarantee always that even if a crash is unavoidable, the severity is minimized.
- inform the occupants adequately about the autonomy and decision state of the system as well as about the driving situation, to ensure that occupant alertness is adequate for the current driving mode. This information is adapted to the occupants’ types and roles, enabling them to respond timely to any required actions.
- inform road users adequately about the systems’ state and intentions and adapts to the user type, thus promoting safe interaction.

AWARE2ALL will pave the way towards the development of an Integral Safety approach to match the demanding requirements of new vehicles addressing diverse SAE automation levels, like L4 with the occupants playing different roles (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Fig. 1. AWARE2ALL overall concept.

The Integral Safety pillar (P1) will integrate components from the two other pillars: exterior (P3) and interior (P2) situation awareness building, using collaborative perception and interaction technologies.

AWARE2ALL will develop new interior and exterior interaction design concepts to optimize the interaction between all scene occupants (interior and exterior). Occupant monitoring and driving readiness assessment will enable reaching an advanced awareness level between the human and the vehicle in all traffic situations, in order to achieve safety and comfort in the emerging automated transport ecosystem.

This approach includes the definition and monitoring of ODD to ensure the safety of the automated driving under all circumstances defining Minimal Risk Manoeuvre and Fallbacks to ensure the safety of both occupants and other traffic participants. AWARE2ALL will advance the information presentation so that the occupant can always fully understand the circumstances under which the automated driving functions are operational, the vehicle's status and the traffic situation.

- **The integral safety system** consists of connected active and passive safety systems. The active safety uses traffic environment information to generate a risk field to optimize the planned trajectories for crash avoidance and/or crash severity mitigation. This information is shared with HRUs via the eHMI. The passive safety system will get the vehicle dynamics prediction information from the active safety system and generate the occupants' body motion prediction for adapting the restraint system activation accordingly. In case that a collision is unavoidable, the HAV would warn the HRUs via the eHMI, iHMI, and OMS.
- **The Human-Centered Cognitive Augmentation (HCCA)** concept involves creating a shared understanding of situation awareness (vehicle/occupants) using iHMI and OMS. It assesses occupant's current states based on various factors like traffic conditions, automation levels, and personal traits. The OMS proposed by AWARE2ALL includes physiological observations and behaviour descriptors. The cognitive augmentation unit calculates differences between optimal and observed values. An adaptive multimodal HMI is adapted on this information. Driver reactions are measured through HMI interaction and OMS feedback, closing the loop. OMS also locates occupants of the vehicle, improving safety systems.
- **Perception system:** allows identification of the external situation of the vehicle and of the HRUs with whom the vehicle must interact. The system will be able to detect and analyse the HRU's attention, through a combination of sensor fusion and object detection that will be performed simultaneously allowing to generate a representative map of the vehicle's environment. 2D image analysis processing will be involved, but also 3D point-clouds generated with LIDAR (useful as validation reference to improve system reliability).
- **Communication system:** allows interaction with HRUs using multi-modal interfaces, like exterior lighting configured according to vehicle's perceived surroundings and by the communication strategy (warning signs, symbols, etc.). Also, new

technologies will be explored, like using microLED for taillights, an immersive technology where the picture elements (pixels) are the light source that is programmable and can be controlled individually to create the patterns, and DLP (Digital Light Processing) or MLA (microlens array) for the use in ground projection. Within the project, different uses of lights will be investigated to determine those with higher impact on the behaviour of road users. The other interface to be explored will be sounds and the use of the AVAS (Acoustic Vehicle Alerting System).

3 AWARE2ALL Use cases

AWARE2ALL systems are currently under development in a total of four demonstrators, one virtual (Demo 1), two physical (Demo 2 and Demo 4) and one hybrid (Demo 3) that will include a physical prototype that will run in a static driving simulator.

Demo 1 - Passive Safety virtual prototype: This demo will include the 3D simulation model of the new vehicle interior configuration with seats, belt systems and airbag systems for crash simulation in LSDyna or PAMcrash. The configurations are defined for forward facing and rearward facing seating positions and cover also one variant for a seat integrated restraint system with advanced body-in-white and interior structure adaptations. The advanced airbag systems will handle the occupant diversity by closed-loop control functions activating variable filling curves and ventilation times³¹ using airbag contact sensor technologies.

Demo 2 – L4 Shuttle Fallback: to showcase an automated L4 shuttle, deploying strategies for fallback and emergency situations on system components/sensors failure including fail-operational functionalities, such as AEB, evasive manoeuvring, or safe/comfortable stops. The systems will exploit V2X interconnection protocols with other agents, including connected vehicles and infrastructure elements.

Demo 3 – iHMI and OMS: a Renault platform driving simulator with environment visualization based on openStreet maps and vehicle dynamics simulation including active safety features. AWARE2ALL OMS and iHMI solutions will be integrated. The Active Safety features will be based on a new trajectory optimization architecture creating a risk field based on object motion prediction, crash severity prediction and ego-motion prediction using a reference path from navigation function.

Demo 4 – eHMI and HRU: based on a Seat or a Cupra platform, that will support in the systems integration. In this vehicle the external perception system will be implemented using the AWARE2ALL platform sensors.

4 Testing and validation approach for AWARE2ALL

AWARE2ALL seeks to expand its comprehension of all the different user and stakeholder groups involved or affected by the safety solutions it develops. This expansion aims to ensure and enhance the inclusion of social groups that are at risk of exclusion. AWARE2ALL embraces principles and practices from the social sciences and humanities (SSH), such as "co-creation" and "inclusive methodology".

Scenarios and use cases will be crafted based on real-world driving situations, considering factors that influence the behavior of HAVs and their interactions with other vehicles and pedestrians. For instance, a scenario might involve an autonomous vehicle navigating a busy urban street during rush hour, where pedestrians are crossing, and vehicles are maneuvering between lanes. Different dimensions are considered:

User Persona Definition: The creation of diverse User Personas is of paramount importance in safety and communication projects involving autonomous vehicles. It is vital to understand the needs and challenges faced by individuals with varying abilities when developing new safety and communication systems for autonomous vehicles. Ensuring the accessibility of these technologies to everyone, regardless of their physical abilities, is a fundamental objective in autonomous vehicle development. Accessibility serves as a cornerstone, guaranteeing the usability of this technology by a wide range of individuals. Age, gender and racial bias represent a significant challenge for HAVs.

Human Road User: When establishing the parameters for defining a scenario, it is imperative to account for the presence of HRU – all individuals involved in the given scenario. In addition to examining their characteristics and the challenges they encounter in their daily lives, it is equally essential to ascertain their roles within our scenario, their geographical positioning, and the activities they might be engaged in. The two primary HRU profiles encompass: (1) **occupants:** individuals situated within the autonomous vehicle; and (2) **VRUs:** as non-motorized road users, such as pedestrians and cyclists, as well as motorcyclists, scooter riders, and individuals with disabilities or those experiencing reduced mobility and orientation.

Road types and infrastructure: Motorways or highways are designed for high-speed travel and are typically multi-lane, predictable and straightforward, with well-marked lanes and limited pedestrian or bicycle traffic. Rural roads are narrow, winding and often lack markings or signage. They may also have unexpected obstacles, such as animals or farm machinery. Urban roads present the most complex challenges for autonomous vehicles. They are crowded, with a wide variety of vehicles, pedestrians and cyclists sharing the same space. In addition, urban roads often have complex traffic patterns, such as one-way streets and roundabouts.

Environment Conditions: Environmental conditions can affect the safety and efficiency of driving on different types of roads, such as motorways, rural roads, and urban roads. Adverse weather conditions, such as fog, rain, or snow, can affect visibility and traction and influence the behavior of both human and autonomous drivers.

5 Safety Parameter Identification and high-level system requirements with KPIs

Evaluating the safety of a system requires the definition of safety parameters, metrics, and the subsequent Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) derived from these metrics. The following definitions clarify these terms in context:

- **Safety Parameters:** These are quantifiable or observable factors directly associated with the safety of road users. They serve as foundational indicators for evaluating safety.

- **New Risks from Automated Driving:** The project addresses novel risks arising from the unique configurations introduced by automated driving. From a passive safety perspective, these new configurations significantly impact seating positions, including rearward-facing positions in the first row of seats..
- **AWARE2ALL's Safety Integration:** AWARE2ALL seeks to incorporate previously marginalized groups into safety assessments and safety development, taking measures to minimize accident severity. The advent of highly automated vehicles introduces new parameters for assessing accident severity, that must account for both unconventional seating positions and the diversity of individuals involved, ensuring consistently high safety standards.
- **Active Vehicle Safety:** to proactively prevent accidents or mitigate high-risk situations to safeguard passengers and external VRUs. The criticality vary for different categories of accident opponents, determined by absolute thresholds or relative weightings of metric numerical values. Developing and evaluating active vehicle safety involves challenges such as determining the relative weights of individual safety parameters and comprehensive safety metrics.

6 Conclusions

This paper presents the first steps of AWARE2ALL project towards the development of new methods and tools to ensure safety of HAVs (shared cars and shuttles) in mixed traffic, protecting both diverse occupants (elderly, disabled, women, men) of the vehicle and the HRUs (VRUs, HDVs) that interact with the vehicle. The AWARE2ALL holistic approach covers the automotive value chain (universities, RTOs, TIER1 and OEM) to support the introduction of HAVs by offering an integral solution able to face future safety critical situations.

7 Acknowledgement

This work was funded by the Horizon Europe programme of the European Union, under grant agreement 101076868 (project AWARE2ALL).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed here are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

1. Anderson, J. M., Kalra, N., Stanley, K. D., Sorensen, P., Samaras, C., Oluwatola, O. A.: Autonomous vehicle technology: a guide for policymakers. Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation (2016)
2. Favaro, F. M., Nader, N., Eurich, S. O., Tripp, M., Varadaraju, N.: Examining accident reports involving autonomous vehicles in California. PLoSone, 12(9), e0184952 (2017).